

Learn2Reg: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Learn2Reg

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

Learn2Reg

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Biomedical image registration is nowadays ubiquitously used in science and hospitals, yet recent research developments do not directly translate into improved clinical workflows. Learn2Reg has consistently worked to bridge this gap by establishing comprehensive metrics for fair evaluation and creating tasks tailored to address critical clinical needs.

Recent advances in deep learning have shifted the research focus of MICCAI toward segmentation and classification, often sidelining the equally critical domain of image registration. Learn2Reg 2025 aims to encourage research in this area, emphasizing the unique challenges posed by the ill-posed nature of registration problems and the need for domain-specific adaptations of learning techniques. The initiative also aims to strengthen connections between research groups working on complementary challenges, encouraging collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Building on the framework and insights of previous years, Learn2Reg 2025 will continue advancing the field of image registration. This edition will serve as a meta-challenge, expanding upon two previous sub-challenges: LUMIR, addressing large-scale unsupervised whole-brain alignment, and ReMIND2Reg, focused on brain multimodal intra-operative registration. While these tasks received substantial contributions in 2024, they remain unsolved and are still far from meeting the standards of clinical acceptance. In this new edition, we aim to build on the progress made, leveraging significant resources, including large datasets and time-consuming annotations, to encourage innovative solutions and further improve results. Our goal is to catalyze advancements that not only address the methodological challenges but also bring these solutions closer to practical clinical application.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

registration, deformable, brain, oncology, multimodal

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

The novelty of Learn2Reg 2025 lies in its focus on two critical yet unsolved tasks, ReMIND2Reg and LUMIR, which tackle challenging problems in biomedical image registration: brain multimodal intra-operative registration and large-scale unsupervised whole-brain alignment, respectively. Despite substantial contributions in 2024, these tasks remain far from achieving the robustness and accuracy required for clinical acceptance.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

ReMIND2Reg: This task addresses a critical application in neurosurgery: optimizing tumor resection to maximize patient outcomes while minimizing neurological deficits. Accurate registration of pre-operative MRI with intra-operative ultrasound (iUS) images is essential for providing surgeons with real-time guidance. This is particularly important in mitigating the effects of brain shift, which causes neuronavigation systems to lose accuracy as surgery progresses due to tissue deformation and resection.

The methods developed in this task will enable:

- Enhanced Surgical Guidance: By aligning pre-operative MRI (T1-weighted and T2-weighted) with intra-operative ultrasound, surgeons can maintain accurate visualization of the tumor and critical brain structures throughout the procedure.
- Improved Patient Outcomes: Precise registration supports achieving the competing goals of maximal tumor resection and minimal damage to healthy tissue, directly influencing recovery and long-term prognosis.
- Wider Accessibility: The use of iUS, a cost-effective and real-time imaging modality, makes this technology adaptable to a broader range of surgical settings compared to intra-operative MRI.

LUMIR: This task focuses on the classical application of brain MRI registration, enabling numerous downstream applications such as atlas construction, shape analysis, and more. Although many deep learning-based models have been proposed for brain MRI registration, there is a lack of large-scale benchmarks, and previous methods have paid less attention to model deployment. This year's LUMIR challenge addresses these gaps by:

- Providing a comprehensive evaluation of both "in-domain" and "out-of-domain" brain registration, utilizing datasets with different MRI sequences, resolutions, and even species for thorough testing.
- Focusing on both model performance and generalizability to ensure the developed models are robust and applicable to diverse scenarios encountered in clinical and neuroscience workflows.

By creating a large-scale benchmark and emphasizing real-world applicability, LUMIR aims to produce models that are not only high-performing but also broadly useful for real-world applications.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

To be determined

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

For both tasks, we expect a similar or larger number of participants as last year:

- ReMIND2Reg:

validation phase: 14 teams and 324 submissions to the leaderboard

testing phase: 5 teams

- LUMIR:

validation phase: 26 teams and 476 submissions to the leaderboard

testing phase: 12 teams

For reference, please see the 2023 Learn2Reg summary paper (<https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2022.3213983>), which had more than 50 contributors.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Following previous Learn2Reg challenge editions, participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

For each task, we plan to write a joint manuscript with the participants summarizing the findings of the 2025 and 2024 editions for each task. We will begin drafting the joint manuscript after MICCAI 2025 concludes and aim to have a draft ready by the MICCAI 2026 call for papers deadline.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Learn2Reg is an off-site challenge, and we will make use of the grand-challenge.org website to host the challenge, evaluation engine, and leaderboards.

On the day of the challenge, a projector, a computer, and two microphones will be needed for the presentations of the winning methods

TASK 1: LUMIR: Large-scale Unsupervised Whole Brain MRI Image Registration

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Subcortical and deep brain structures are involved in many cognitive, memory, and emotional tasks. The hippocampus, e.g., is known to be involved in aging, memory, and spatial navigation. Regional analysis of whole brain MRI has also been identified as a key indicator for pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease, schizophrenia, and epilepsy. The challenge in this task is the alignment of small structures of variable shape and size with high precision on mono-modal MRI images between different patients.

The previous LUMIR challenge at Learn2Reg inspired the scientific community to tackle brain registration problems using unsupervised learning-based methods. As the first of its kind to feature such a large-scale imaging dataset, the LUMIR challenge marked a significant step toward developing foundational brain registration models. A key finding from last year's LUMIR challenge was that models trained on T1 MRI images demonstrated surprising generalizability to out-of-domain MRI sequences and resolutions, such as T2 images and ultra-high-field MRIs. Building on this insight, this year's LUMIR challenge introduces two significant innovations: (1) an extended dataset with additional manually annotated fiducial markers for more precise evaluation, and (2) zero-shot registration tasks to assess model generalizability on unseen brain MRI sequences and resolutions.

This year's challenge includes an "in-domain" dataset with over 4,000 neuroimaging datasets from the previous challenge and an "out-of-domain" dataset comprising more than 3,000 diverse neuroimages. The "out-of-domain" dataset features varying MRI sequences, resolutions, and brain diseases, enabling rigorous evaluation of the zero-shot capabilities of learning-based registration models. Segmentation maps for 133 cortical and subcortical regions were generated for all images using the SLANT segmentation method. Furthermore, for the "in-domain" dataset, 124 brain MRIs with manually labeled fiducial markers have been added in-addition to last year's set of 131 manually labeled images, enabling more robust quantification of registration accuracy. We will also provide manually labeled fiducial markers to 250 "out-of-domain" dataset for further evaluation. Participants will receive preprocessed images for 3,494 subjects (training and validation) while label maps and fiducial markers will remain confidential for evaluation purposes. This large-scale dataset and zero-shot framework aim to advance the development of foundational models for brain image registration and establish new benchmarks for both in-domain and out-of-domain registration.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Registration, deformable, brain, multimodal

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Junyu Chen (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

Yihao Liu (Vanderbilt University, TN, USA)

Shuwen Wei (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

Harrison Bai (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

Aaron Carass (Johns Hopkins University, MD, USA)

Mattias Heinrich (University of Lübeck, Lübeck, Germany)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Junyu Chen (jchen245@jhmi.edu)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://learn2reg.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Private data is allowed but must be reported

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Organizers and team members of organizers may participate and are ranked but cannot win prizes.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

TBA

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Challenge organizers may submit algorithms as baselines but cannot win prizes. Up to three (different) teams can win awards.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

Participants in the test phase will also be invited to co-author the joint manuscript summarizing the challenge. Each team may contribute up to two authors, ideally the primary contributor and their senior author.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The validation and test submission processes are different:

- Validation leaderboard: The participating teams must submit their predictions (displacement fields) as a single compressed zip file via the grand-challenge.org interface. The tree directory structure will be described once the challenge is online.

- Test leaderboard: the participating teams are required to submit a short paper describing their method and a Docker container containing pre-trained models and training code. We encourage participants to only submit containers that can be run in a rootless mode to increase the usability of the submitted Docker containers on computational servers.

This choice is a trade-off between reducing the participant's workload and limiting the risk of cheating for the final ranking.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will get the opportunity to upload their algorithm output to be evaluated on the validation data of the validation phase in order to avoid any pitfalls (wrong orientation, etc.). We also provide our evaluation scripts to test them on the training data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration period: March 2025
 - Release date of the training set: March 2025
 - Release date of the validation set: March 2025
 - Start of the validation phase: April 2025
 - Start of the evaluation phase: August 2025
 - End of the evaluation phase: mid-August 2025 (short description of the proposed technique, results on the validation set)
 - MICCAI 2025: presentation of results

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

If necessary (e.g. not the case for already open-sourced data) ethics approval will be requested prior to releasing any new data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)

- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code to evaluate performance is available at:

https://github.com/JHU-MedImage-Reg/LUMIR_L2R

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are encouraged but not required to make their code publicly available. We will provide links to available source code on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Data providers who annotate test cases have access to test labels (of specific sub-task), organizers who implement evaluation metrics and scripts will have partial access to test labels. This means that personnel responsible for implementing evaluation scripts will be provided with a limited set of example labels for troubleshooting and internal code testing. However, to maintain the privacy of the test data, full access to test labels will be strictly restricted to a minimal number of personnel.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research

- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Prognosis, Intervention planning, Intervention follow up, Diagnosis, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Neuroimaging registration is an important part of neuroscience and clinical treatment and planning for a wide range of diseases and procedures, such as neurodegenerative diseases (AD, schizophrenia, epilepsy) or tumor resections.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The “in-domain” dataset consists of T1-weighted MRIs sourced from the OpenBHB project. A specific subset of the OpenBHB dataset was selected, including scans from 10 publicly available datasets, exclusively comprising healthy control subjects (male and female) with an average age of 24.9 ± 14.3 years.

The “out-of-domain” dataset is derived from five publicly accessible datasets: ADHD [3,4], ADNI1 [5], NIMH [6],

UltraCortex [7], and Macaque [8]. The ADHD dataset includes MRI scans from 47 children diagnosed with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), comprising 35 males (ages 8.59–11.85) and 12 females (ages 9.8–12.3). The ADNI1 dataset features scans from 728 subjects diagnosed with Alzheimer’s disease, aged 55–91 years. The NIMH dataset includes T1-, T2-, T2*-, and FLAIR-weighted MRI scans from 249 healthy subjects aged 18–72 years. The UltraCortex dataset consists of MRI scans from 78 healthy subjects aged 20–53 years. Finally, the Macaque dataset contains T1-weighted brain MRI scans from 56 macaques.

1. Benoit Dufumier, Antoine Grigis, Julie Victor, Corentin Ambroise, Vincent Frouin, Edouard Duchesnay, December 8, 2021, "OpenBHB: a Multi-Site Brain MRI Dataset for Age Prediction and Debiasing", IEEE Dataport, doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/7jsg-jx57>.
2. Taha, Alaa, et al. "Magnetic resonance imaging datasets with anatomical fiducials for quality control and registration." *Scientific Data* 10.1 (2023): 449.
3. M. N. Lytle, R. Hammer, and J. R. Booth, "A neuroimaging dataset on working memory and reward processing in children with and without adhd," *Data in Brief*, vol. 31, p. 105801, 2020.
4. M. N. Lytle, D. D. Burman, and J. R. Booth, "A neuroimaging dataset on response inhibition and selective attention in adults and children with and without adhd," *Data in Brief*, vol. 37, p. 107158, 2021
5. Weiner, M. W., Veitch, D. P., Aisen, P. S., Beckett, L. A., Cairns, N. J., Green, R. C., ... & Trojanowski, J. Q. (2013). The Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative: a review of papers published since its inception. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 9(5), e111-e194.
6. A. C. Nugent, A. G. Thomas, M. Mahoney, A. Gibbons, J. T. Smith, A. J. Charles, J. S. Shaw, J. D. Stout, A. M. Namyst, A. Basavaraj et al., "The nimh intramural healthy volunteer dataset: A comprehensive meg, mri, and behavioral resource," *Scientific Data*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 518, 2022
7. L. Mahler, J. Steiglechner, B. Bender, T. Lindig, D. Ramadan, J. Bause, F. Birk, R. Heule, E. Charyasz, M. Erb et al., "Ultracortex: Submillimeter ultra-high field 9.4 t brain mr image collection and manual cortical segmentations," *bioRxiv*, pp. 2024–06, 2024.
8. M. P. Milham, L. Ai, B. Koo, T. Xu, C. Amiez, F. Balezeau, M. G. Baxter, E. L. Blezer, T. Brochier, A. Chen et al., "An open resource for non-human primate imaging," *Neuron*, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 61–74, 2018.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) - T1-weighted, T2-weighted, T2*-weighted, and FLAIR brain MRI.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The "in-domain" dataset is adapted from the OpenBHB dataset, comprising 3,984 T1-weighted MRI scans of healthy brains collected from over 60 centers worldwide. These scans underwent preprocessing with FreeSurfer, including pre-affine registration and skull-stripping. Additional preprocessing steps included intensity normalization and automatic segmentation to generate label maps for 133 anatomical structures. The dataset is divided into three subsets: 3,384 for training, 100 for validation, and 500 for testing.

The "out-of-domain" dataset is adapted from five sources: ADHD, ADNI1, NIMH, UltraCortex, and Macaque,

comprising a total of 1,158 subjects. While participants are provided only with T1-weighted MRI scans of healthy adult subjects for training, the “out-of-domain” dataset is designed to facilitate challenging out-of-domain registration tasks. These include inter-subject registration of T1-weighted MRI scans from pathological brains (e.g., Alzheimer’s disease), pediatric brains (under 18 years of age), and scans involving T1-, T2-, T2*-, and FLAIR-weighted MRI sequences. Additionally, a T1-weighted atlas image is included for atlas-to-subject registration tasks. The dataset comprises 3,362 image pairs for zero-shot evaluation, divided into 100 for validation and 3,262 for testing.

For all images, we applied consistent preprocessing steps, including intensity normalization, skull-stripping, and pre-affine registration. Automatic segmentation was performed to generate label maps for 133 anatomical structures. Furthermore, 255 scans from the “in-domain” dataset include manually annotated fiducial markers for 32 anatomical features.

For the Learn2Reg challenge, only the preprocessed images will be provided. Label maps and fiducial markers will remain confidential, aligning with the challenge’s focus on unsupervised image registration.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

-The “in-domain” dataset:

The OpenBHB dataset comprises only healthy control subjects of both genders.

-The “out-of-domain” dataset:

The ADHD comprises children subjects diagnosed with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), comprising 35 males (ages 8.59–11.85) and 12 females (ages 9.8–12.3). The ADNI1 dataset features scans from 728 subjects diagnosed with Alzheimer’s disease, aged 55–91 years. The NIMH dataset includes T1-, T2-, T2*-, and FLAIR-weighted MRI scans from 249 healthy subjects aged 18–72 years. The UltraCortex dataset consists of MRI scans from 78 healthy subjects aged 20–53 years. Finally, the Macaque dataset contains T1-weighted brain MRI scans from 56 macaques.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Whole brain MRI showing important neuroanatomical regions: cortical, subcortical and deep brain structures.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Highly accurate alignment of subcortical and deep brain anatomy across patients within the same modality (MRI).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that

assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Reliability,Robustness,Runtime,Complexity

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

-Imaging data are sourced from multiple public datasets, encompassing a wide range of MRI systems and protocols from centers worldwide.

-Fiducial markers are manually annotated by physicians using 3D Slicer.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Data is either acquired or normalized to 1x1x1 mm isotropic resolution of MRI whole brain scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The “in-domain” dataset, OpenBHB dataset [1], accessible at <https://baobablab.github.io/bhb/dataset>, features image data compiled from 10 publicly available datasets, originating from over 60 centers globally. Detailed information about the acquisition protocols and the specific scans utilized is available in the official documents of each contributing dataset:

- ABIDE 1 [2]
- ABIDE 2 [3]
- CoRR [4]
- GSP [5]
- IXI [6]
- Localizer [7]
- MPI-Leipzig [8]
- NAR [9]
- NPC [10]
- RBP [11, 12]

The “out-of-domain” dataset are obtained from 5 publicly available datasets. Detailed information about the acquisition protocols and the specific scans utilized is available in the official documents of each contributing dataset:

- ADHD [13,14]
- ADNI1 [15]
- NIMH [16]

- UltraCortex 9.4T [17]
- Macaque [18]

1. Benoit Dufumier, Antoine Grigis, Julie Victor, Corentin Ambroise, Vincent Frouin, Edouard Duchesnay, December 8, 2021, "OpenBHB: a Multi-Site Brain MRI Dataset for Age Prediction and Debiasing", IEEE Dataport, doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/7jsg-jx57>.
2. http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/abide/abide_I.html
3. http://fcon_1000.projects.nitrc.org/indi/abide/abide_II.html
4. Zuo, Xi-Nian, et al. "An open science resource for establishing reliability and reproducibility in functional connectomics." *Scientific data* 1.1 (2014): 1-13.
5. Buckner, Randy L.; Roffman, Joshua L.; Smoller, Jordan W., 2014, "Brain Genomics Superstruct Project (GSP)", <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/25833>, Harvard Dataverse, V10
6. <https://brain-development.org/ixi-dataset>
7. Orfanos, D. P., et al. (2017). The brainomics/localizer database. *NeuroImage*, 144, 309-314.
8. Babayan, A., et al. (2019). A mind-brain-body dataset of MRI, EEG, cognition, emotion, and peripheral physiology in young and old adults. *Scientific data*, 6(1), 1-21.
9. Nastase, S. A., et al. (2021). The "Narratives" fMRI dataset for evaluating models of naturalistic language comprehension. *Scientific data*, 8(1), 250.
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11. Li, P., & Clariana, R. B. (2019). Reading comprehension in L1 and L2: An integrative approach. *Journal of Neurolinguistics*, 50, 94-105.
12. Follmer, D. J., et al. (2018). What predicts adult readers' understanding of STEM texts?. *Reading and Writing*, 31, 185-214.
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16. A. C. Nugent, A. G. Thomas, M. Mahoney, A. Gibbons, J. T. Smith, A. J. Charles, J. S. Shaw, J. D. Stout, A. M. Namyst, A. Basavaraj et al., "The nimh intramural healthy volunteer dataset: A comprehensive meg, mri, and behavioral resource," *Scientific Data*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 518, 2022
17. L. Mahler, J. Steiglechner, B. Bender, T. Lindig, D. Ramadan, J. Bause, F. Birk, R. Heule, E. Charyasz, M. Erb et al., "Ultracortex: Submillimeter ultra-high field 9.4 t brain mr image collection and manual cortical segmentations," *bioRxiv*, pp. 2024-06, 2024.
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d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Not applicable.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to a single brain MRI volume. The brain MRI images are annotated with segmentations according to the same protocol. Meanwhile, the portion of the dataset feature fiducial markers that are placed manually.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 3384 (In-domain dataset - images only)

Validation: 50 (In-domain dataset - segmentation) + 50 (In-domain dataset - fiducial markers) + 50 (Out-of-domain dataset - segmentation) + 50 (Out-of-domain dataset - fiducial markers)

Testing: 245 (In-domain dataset - segmentation) + 205 (In-domain dataset - fiducial markers) + 3,062 (Out-of-domain dataset - segmentation) + 200 (Out-of-domain dataset - fiducial markers)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

A substantial number of images from the in-domain dataset are used to effectively train and evaluate the deep neural networks designed for brain MRI registration. Similarly, a significant volume of out-of-domain images is employed to rigorously assess the generalizability of the developed registration models. To enhance the evaluation, we include a large set of anatomical label maps and manually annotated fiducial markers, which are exclusively reserved for validation and assessment, providing an additional measure of registration accuracy. With the extensive training, validation, and test datasets allocated, we can perform statistical analyses to identify the top-performing registration models for brain MRI.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

In the inter-subject registration task, all potential pairs can be employed for training and evaluation. To limit the amount of test transformations to be processed, we will announce around 4,000 randomly selected pairs of test subjects that should be registered for evaluation.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Although the imaging data are publicly available, the segmentation masks and fiducial markers used for evaluation remain unpublished.

Validation: 100 label maps + 100 sets of fiducial markers

Testing: 3307 label maps + 405 sets of fiducial markers

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For the manually annotated fiducial markers, we followed the annotation protocol outlined in prior work [2]. The annotations were performed by two neurologists and subsequently validated by an experienced radiologist at Johns Hopkins University. The anatomical label maps were generated using SLANT [1], an automatic segmentation method that identifies 133 anatomical structures. Additionally, we plan to annotate 250 MRI scans from the out-of-domain dataset with fiducial markers for validation and testing purposes, adhering to the methodology described in [2]. For the Learn2Reg challenge, only the preprocessed images for the 3,464 training and validation subjects will be shared; segmentation labels and fiducial markers will remain confidential.

1. Huo, Yuankai, et al. "3D whole brain segmentation using spatially localized atlas network tiles." *NeuroImage* 194 (2019): 105-119.

2. Taha, Alaa, et al. "Magnetic resonance imaging datasets with anatomical fiducials for quality control and registration." *Scientific Data* 10.1 (2023): 449.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The fiducial markers were annotated following the protocol established in a previous independent study. The detailed protocol is available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-023-02330-9>.

Taha, Alaa, et al. "Magnetic resonance imaging datasets with anatomical fiducials for quality control and registration." *Scientific Data* 10.1 (2023): 449.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

SLANT [1] is a widely recognized and established method for automatic whole brain segmentation in neuroimaging. The fiducial markers were annotated following the protocol established in a previous independent study [2]. Dr. Harrison Bai, an experienced radiologist with over nine years of experience in the field of radiology and more than ten years in medicine, currently serving as an Associate Professor at Johns Hopkins, will undertake the manual annotation for the subset of the out-of-domain dataset in collaboration with two experienced neurologists.

1. Huo, Yuankai, et al. "3D whole brain segmentation using spatially localized atlas network tiles." *NeuroImage* 194 (2019): 105-119.

2. Taha, Alaa, et al. "Magnetic resonance imaging datasets with anatomical fiducials for quality control and registration." *Scientific Data* 10.1 (2023): 449.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

To merge multiple annotations, an average was calculated from the fiducial markers placed by different raters.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Standard neuroimaging pre-processing pipeline was used, including resampling to isotropic voxel resolution, intensity normalization, skull-stripping, ensuring consistent spatial dimensions, and providing affine pre-registration. These steps are intended to simplify the application of learning-based algorithms for participants who have limited experience in image registration. The same pre-processing pipeline was deployed for the training, validation, and testing cases.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Previous research has demonstrated that the automatic segmentation tool SLANT [1] attains over 75% Dice overlap for all 133 structures, though this varies considerably among them. Note that SLANT significantly surpasses many of the traditional state-of-the-art methods of its time in terms of both speed and accuracy. However, it faces challenges with certain small structures, such as the inferior horn of the lateral ventricle and the cortex, where there is often inadequate resolution or contrast.

The fiducial marker annotations were performed following the protocol outlined in a prior study, which reported an inter-rater variability of 1.48 ± 0.34 mm. This was calculated by dividing the sum of the pairwise Euclidean distances (as represented by the sigma notation) by the total number of pairwise distances across the dataset [2]. We anticipate similar variability in the labeling of our fiducial markers.

1. Huo, Yuankai, et al. "3D whole brain segmentation using spatially localized atlas network tiles." *NeuroImage* 194 (2019): 105-119.

2. Taha, Alaa, et al. "Magnetic resonance imaging datasets with anatomical fiducials for quality control and registration." *Scientific Data* 10.1 (2023): 449.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not applicable.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

-DSC/HD95: The deformation fields generated by the methods of challenge participants will be applied to deform the label maps of the moving images. Subsequently, the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and the 95 percentile of the Hausdorff distance (HD95) metrics will be calculated by comparing the deformed label maps with the label maps of the fixed images, with the results being averaged over all anatomical structures and subjects.

-TRE: The deformation fields generated by the methods of challenge participants will be applied to displace the fiducial markers placed on the moving images. Subsequently, the target registration error (TRE) will be calculated as the distance between the displaced fiducial markers with the fiducial markers in the fixed images, with the results being averaged over all markers and subjects.

-Deformation regularity: The smoothness and regularity of the deformation fields produced by the challenge participants' methods will be assessed and averaged over all subjects.

- 1) DSC of segmentations
- 2) HD95 (95% percentile of Hausdorff distance) of segmentations
- 3) TRE of fiducial markers
- 4) Robustness: 30% lowest DSC/TRE of all cases
- 5) Percentage of non-diffeomorphic volume
- 6) Run-time computation time

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

DSC or TRE respectively measure accuracy; HD95 measures reliability; Outliers are penalized with the robustness score (30% of lowest mean DSC or 30% of highest mean TRE). Furthermore, the deformation regularity, indicated by the percentage of non-positive Jacobian determinant and non-diffeomorphic volume [1], measures the models' tendency to produce physically implausible behaviors. Finally, run-time computation time is relevant for clinical applications.

1. Liu, Yihao, et al. "On finite difference jacobian computation in deformable image registration." (2024). International Journal of Computer Vision.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

All metrics but robustness-based metrics use mean rank per case (ranks are normalized to between 0.1 and 1, higher being better). For multi-label tasks the ranks are computed per structure and later averaged. As done in the Medical Segmentation Decathlon we will employ "significant ranks"

<http://medicaldecathlon.com/files/MSD-Ranking-scheme.pdf>

Across all metrics an overall score is aggregated using the geometric mean. This encourages consistency across criteria. We will compute two separate rankings with and without including runtime, the one without will be considered for awards.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Participants submit their algorithms as Docker containers during the final test phase, which the organizers execute on every test pair, ensuring that results are consistently available for all submissions. Therefore, no cases

of missing results were expected.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

All metrics but robustness-based metrics use mean rank per case (ranks are normalized to between 0.1 and 1, higher being better). As done in the Medical Segmentation Decathlon we will employ "significant ranks" <http://medicaldecathlon.com/files/MSD-Ranking-scheme.pdf>. Across all metrics, an overall score is aggregated using the geometric mean. This encourages consistency across criteria. A ten-fold difference between highest and lowest score is fixed to be independent of the number of participants.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The ranking scheme is in principle based on the ranking scheme of the Medical Decathlon. We rank methods using statistically significantly different results. For each metric applied in the task, methods are compared against each other (Wilcoxon signed rank test with $p < 0.05$, see details in [code\[https://github.com/MDL-UzL/L2R/tree/main/ranking\]](https://github.com/MDL-UzL/L2R/tree/main/ranking)), ranked based on the number of "won" comparisons and finally mapped to a numerical metric rank score between 0.1 and 1 (with possible score sharing). A task rank score is then computed as the geometric mean of individual metric rank scores. Ties will result in an average rank among all equal participants.

Given the variability in dataset sizes across different "out-of-domain" subtasks and the numerous anatomical structures in the label maps, a detailed analysis of each subtask and a comparison across anatomical structures will be thoroughly discussed in the joint manuscript.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The geometric mean is more robust against outliers, hence methods that perform well on all metrics are encouraged.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We will provide several baseline algorithms to compare new methods against, there are:

- VoxelMorph (IEEE TMI'19)
- TransMorph (MedIA'22)

- VFA (SPIE JMI'24)
- ANTs, NiftyReg, Deeds

TASK 2: ReMIND2Reg: Brain Resection Multimodal Registration

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Surgical resection is the critical first step for treating most brain tumors, and the extent of resection is the major modifiable determinant of patient outcome. To optimize outcomes, surgeons must avoid causing neurologic deficits while leaving as little residual tumor as possible. To reach these competing objectives, intraoperative ultrasound (iUS) has raised attention as it is an affordable, real-time, and intraoperative imaging technology that can be easily integrated into existing surgical workflows, especially when compared with intraoperative Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). In parallel, neuronavigation has helped considerably in providing intraoperative guidance to surgeons, allowing them to visualize the location of their surgical instruments relative to the tumor and critical brain structures visible in preoperative MRI. However, the utility of neuronavigation decreases as surgery progresses due to brain shift, which is caused by brain deformation and tissue resection during surgery, leaving surgeons without guidance.

The goal of the ReMIND-Learn2Reg challenge task is to register multi-parametric pre-operative MRI and intra-operative 3D ultrasound images. Specifically, we focus on the challenging problem of pre-operative to post-resection registration, requiring the estimation of large deformations and tissue resections. Preoperative MRI comprises two structural MRI sequences: contrast-enhanced T1-weighted (ceT1) and native T2-weighted (T2). However, not all sequences will be available for all cases. For this reason, developed methods must have the flexibility to leverage incomplete sets of data at inference time. To tackle this challenging registration task, we provide a large non-annotated training set (N=99, 99 3D iUS, 93 ceT1, and 62 T2). Evaluation will be performed using manual landmarks on a private set (N=10, 10 T2-iUS pairs + 10 ceT1-US pairs).

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

registration, deformable, brain, oncology, multimodal, realtime

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Reuben Dorent (Inria, Paris, France)

Olivier Colliot (Inria, Paris, France)

William Wells (Harvard, Boston, USA)

Tina Kapur (Harvard, Boston, USA)

Alexandra Golby (Harvard, Boston, USA)

Mattias Heinrich (University of Lübeck, Lübeck, Germany)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Reuben Dorent (reuben.dorent@inria.fr)

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://learn2reg.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

Organizers and team members of organizers may participate and are ranked but cannot win prizes.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We are hoping for a sponsor from a company.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.

- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Challenge organizers may submit algorithms as baselines but cannot win prizes. Up to three (different) teams can win awards.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participants must submit a short description of their methods via arXiv, based on their leaderboard results, to be eligible for test phase participation. Selected participants who contribute to the test phase will later (after the challenge concludes) be invited to submit a more detailed method description. These submissions will be compiled into the Learn2Reg proceedings, which may be published as an arXiv collection or included in open-access journals such as MELBA.

Participants in the test phase will also be invited to co-author the joint manuscript summarizing the challenge. Each team may contribute up to two authors, ideally the primary contributor and their senior author.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The validation and test submission processes are different:

- Validation leaderboard: The participating teams must submit their predictions (displacement fields) as a single compressed zip file via the grand-challenge.org interface. The tree directory structure will be described once the challenge is online.

- Test leaderboard: the participating teams are required to submit a short paper describing their method and a Docker container containing pre-trained models and training code. We encourage participants to only submit containers that can be run in a rootless mode to increase the usability of the submitted Docker containers on computational servers.

This choice is a trade-off between reducing the participant's workload and limiting the risk of cheating for the final ranking.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will get the opportunity to upload their algorithm output to be evaluated on the validation data of the validation phase in order to avoid any pitfalls (wrong orientation, etc.). We also provide our evaluation scripts to test them on the training data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Registration period: March 2025
 - Release date of the training set: March 2025
 - Release date of the validation set: March 2025
 - Start of the validation phase: April 2025
 - Start of the evaluation phase: July 2025
 - End of the evaluation phase: August 2025 (short description of the proposed technique, results on the validation set)
 - MICCAI 2025: presentation of results

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Collection, analysis, and release of the ReMIND database have been performed in compliance with all relevant ethical regulations. The Institutional Review Board at the Brigham and Women's Hospital approved the protocol (2002-P-001238), and informed consent was obtained from all participants, including for public sharing of data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation code to evaluate performance is available at:

<https://github.com/ReubenDo/ReMIND2Reg/tree/main/evaluation>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are encouraged but not required to make their code publicly available. We will provide links to available source code on the challenge website.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Data providers who annotate test and validation cases will have access to the landmarks.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Surgery, Assistance, Longitudinal study

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection

- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

A variety of patient cohorts can benefit from improved medical image registration between pre-operative MR data and intraoperative ultrasound images. It especially includes brain, spine, prostate, and liver image-guided interventions.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort consists of subjects who are surgically treated with image-guided tumor resection and for whom pre-operative MRI and 3D intra-operative ultrasound data have been acquired.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Intraoperative Ultrasound (iUS), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The images will be released in compressed Nifti (.nii.gz) files. The image orientation and the voxel size can be found in these files.

As the registration task is unsupervised, no annotations are given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No further information is given.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The MRI data of the brain was acquired before the surgery, and the ultrasound data was acquired after substantial tumor resection was completed to the degree that either the surgeon was satisfied with the microscopically visible extent of resection or to identify the remaining portion of the tumor.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Tissue deformation induced by brain tumor resection.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Complexity,Robustness,Applicability,Runtime,Accuracy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

MR data: These scans were acquired using 3T scanners from various manufacturers (Siemens, GE).

iUS data: All iUS series were acquired using a sterilizable 2D neuro-cranial curvilinear transducer on a cart-based ultrasound system (N13C5, BK5000, GE Healthcare, Peabody, MA, USA) in the AMIGO suite. The "Ultrasound Navigation Adapter Array" together with the "Ultrasound Navigation Adapter Base - BK N13C5" (Brainlab AG, Munich, Germany) were attached to the iUS probe to enable the Curve platform to track the probe relative to the patient. This enabled the reconstruction of a 3D volume from the tracked 2D sweeps using the "Ultrasound" module within the "Elements" software platform on the "Curve" hardware system.

More details can be found in our data paper: DOI: 10.1101/2023.09.14.23295596.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The MR data include different 3D sequences (contrast-enhanced T1 and T2) scans. Not all sequences are available for all patients. Contrast-enhanced T1 images were acquired using MP-RAGE sequences from different manufacturers. T2 images were acquired using the SPACE protocol with Siemens scanners (3T).

The ultrasound probe had a contact area of 29mm x 10mm and a frequency range of 5-13 MHz. The imaging plane was chosen to be as parallel as possible to one of the three cardinal axes of the head (axial, sagittal, coronal). However, this was often limited by the size and shape of the craniotomy. The transducer was swept unidirectionally at a slow, consistent speed through the craniotomy. As mentioned above, 3D reconstruction was performed using the built-in proprietary reconstruction method in the Brainlab system.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

MR data: multi-institutional (USA)

Ultrasound data: Brigham and Women's Hospital, Boston, MA, USA

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Surgeon

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 99 cases with 99 post-resection 3D iUS (99) 99 3D iUS and 93 pre-operative ceT1 and 62 pre-operative T2.

Validation: 5 cases with post-resection 3D iUS and both (ceT1 and T2) pre-operative MR images.

Consequently, a total of 10 predictions will be evaluated on the validation set: 5 predictions using only ceT1, and 5 using T2 as input.

Test: 10 cases have been annotated for both ceT1 and T2. Consequently, a total of 20 predictions will be evaluated on the test set: 10 predictions using only ceT1, and 10 predictions using only T2.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The training and validation sets correspond to a subset of the ReMIND dataset available on TCIA, where both pre-dura and post-resection ultrasound images were acquired. Moreover, only 3D MR data is used in this

challenge.

The testing set corresponds to the consecutive cases that were surgically treated at the same institution. Providing corresponding landmarks in multimodal scans is very time-consuming (>3 hours per case) and only possible for domain experts.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The landmarks of the validation data are not released, only the evaluation code is released. Moreover, the test data is private (10 cases) and has not been published somewhere else.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We do not expect any difference between the training, validation, and test cases. They correspond to consecutive cases.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

2 annotators.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

First, salient features were automatically detected in the ultrasound volumes before dural opening (data not included in this challenge) and after resection.

The features identified in the pre-dura images were then be transferred to the pre-operative MR space using affine image registration, which is a solved problem given the absence of deformation and the good initialization provided by the navigation system.

Subsequently, two raters manually identified approximately 10 matches for each pair of data. Anatomical landmarks eligible for matching include deep grooves and corners of sulci, convex points of gyri, and vanishing points of sulci. In cases where raters disagree on matches (one accepts, and the other does not), a consensus was reached through a joint investigation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Two medical imaging experts who have +5 years of experience in brain anatomy.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotations were performed simultaneously by the two imaging experts. Each landmark was reviewed by each annotator at the time of investigation and refined if needed until both raters agreed.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Common pre-processing to the same voxel resolution (0.5x0.5x0.5mm) and spatial dimension are performed to ease the use of learning-based algorithms for participants with little prior experience in image registration. Pre-operative MR images are co-registered using NiftyReg.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The inter-rater variability between pre-dura and post-resection was found to be equal to 1.89 ± 0.37 mm in a previous study using a similar annotating technique. As we now add an extra step (transferring to the MR data), this inter-rater variability may be higher.

For the 2025 edition, we will estimate the inter-rater variability by presenting features in the post-resection volume. Each expert will then be asked to manually locate the correspondence for the post-resection feature in the MR data.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

Not applicable.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

- 1) Mean Target Registration Error (mTRE) of manually annotated landmarks
- 2) Robustness: 30% highest TRE of all cases
- 3) Run-time computation time

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

TRE measures accuracy; Outliers are penalized with the robustness score (30% of highest mean TRE).

Run-time computation time is relevant for clinical applications.

The percentage of non-diffeomorphic volume metric is not used in ReMIND2Reg subtask because this task involves registering images acquired before and after surgical resection, which introduces substantial topological changes. Since the predicted transformations must account for tissue resection, they are not expected to be diffeomorphic or smooth.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The geometric mean encourages consistency across criteria. A ten-fold difference between the highest and lowest scores is fixed to be independent of the number of participants. We will compute two separate rankings with and without including runtime, the one without will be considered for awards.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Participants submit their algorithms as Docker containers during the final test phase, which the organizers execute on every test pair, ensuring that results are consistently available for all submissions. Therefore, no cases of missing results were expected.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

All metrics but robustness-based metrics use mean rank per case (ranks are normalized to between 0.1 and 1, higher being better). As done in the Medical Segmentation Decathlon we will employ "significant ranks" <http://medicaldecathlon.com/files/MSD-Ranking-scheme.pdf>. Across all metrics, an overall score is aggregated using the geometric mean. This encourages consistency across criteria. A ten-fold difference between highest and lowest score is fixed to be independent of the number of participants.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The ranking scheme is, in principle, based on the ranking scheme of the Medical Decathlon. We rank methods using statistically significantly different results. For each metric applied in a task, methods are compared against each other (Wilcoxon signed rank test with $p < 0.05$, see details in code [<https://github.com/MDL-UzL/L2R/tree/main/ranking>]), ranked based on the number of "won" comparisons and finally mapped to a numerical metric rank score between 0.1 and 1 (with possible score sharing). A task rank score is then computed as the geometric mean of individual metric rank scores. Ties will result in an average rank among all equal participants.

This year, we will benefit from the expertise of Prof. O. Colliot's team to incorporate confidence intervals into the evaluation framework, allowing us to better characterize the uncertainty in the performance of image-registration algorithms. Given the unique challenges posed by the data, including:

- 1) The non-independent and identically distributed (non-i.i.d.) nature of the landmarks, and
- 2) The imbalance in the number of landmarks per case,

we plan to adopt a hierarchical statistical approach. Specifically, this approach will model variability at multiple levels, such as within each case and across the dataset as a whole. This methodology will provide more robust

and reliable performance metrics.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The geometric mean is more robust against outliers, hence methods that perform well on all metrics are encouraged.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

We provide several baseline algorithms to compare new methods against, there are:

- NiftyReg
- ConvexAdam
- Deeds

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A